

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions. Part-XIII : Microwave irradiation assisted synthesis and spectroscopic investigations of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl and *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones¹

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Abstract : *C*-Aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones have been prepared in very high yields from *N*-phenylhydroxylamine and aryl aldehydes using the microwave irradiation technique within a few minutes. The synthesis of a new series of nitrones, viz. the series of *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones were also achieved by this technique. Systematic and detailed spectroscopic investigations of all these nitrones were undertaken and some generalisations made regarding their spectroscopical properties.

Keywords : *C*-Aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones, *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones, microwave irradiation.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions constitute a major synthetic route for construction of heterocyclic rings. Nitronc cycloadditions, which have been widely investigated, lead to reduced isoxazole systems²⁻⁴. Our interest in nitronc cycloadditions⁵ led us to develop a fast high-yielding procedure for the synthesis of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones based on the application of the microwave irradiation technique^{6,7}. The conventional method^{5,6} for the synthesis of this type of diaryl nitrones consists of heating a mixture of the starting materials in ethanol for periods varying from half to 2 h. A new series of nitrones, viz. the *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones, were also synthesised in the course of the present work.

All the nitrones (1-14) belonging to the two series, mentioned in this communication, were synthesised from

aromatic aldehydes and the corresponding *N*-phenylhydroxylamine in excellent yields within a few minutes in methylene chloride solution utilising the microwave irradiation technique.

Results and discussion

In a typical procedure the aromatic aldehyde was taken with a small excess of *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (1 : 1.2-1.3 molar ratio) in anhydrous dichloromethane in an Erlenmeyer flask. The reaction mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation for periods varying from 1-4 min; on occasion this was extended to 15 min. The reaction mixture was analysed by 300 MHz ¹H NMR of aliquots taken after intervals of 1 min. The post-reaction mixture was diluted with chloroform and evaporated to dryness in a rotary evaporator

Table 1. Microwave irradiation assisted synthesis of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones

Sl. no.	Substituted benzaldehyde R-C ₆ H ₄ CHO; R ≡	Nitrones obtained	Reaction times, in minutes NMR monitoring of percentage yield			Later measurements	Isolated ^a percentage yield and reaction ^a time in minutes	
			1 min	2 min	3 min			
1.	H	1	93	92		91.5 (4 min)	87	1
2.	4-NO ₂	2	96	95.5	95.5		90	1
3.	3-NO ₂	3	85	88	88		80	2
4.	4-Cl	4	78	75	73		73	1
5.	3-Cl	5	88	87	86.5		82	1
6.	4-Br	6	81	80	80		77	1
7.	4-OMe	7	–	–	77.5	78 (15 min)	70	6
8.	2-OMe	8	–	–	97	96.5 (6 min) 94.5 (15 min)	91	3
9.	Cinnamaldehyde	9	81	82.5	81	–	74	1

^aFrom a second set of experiments – other than those used for monitoring.

Note : Percentage conversions as determined by 300 MHz ¹H NMR analysis were as follows : after 1 min : 1-93%; 2-96%; 5-88%; 6-81%; 3-88%; after 3 min : 8-97%; 4-78%; after 1 min, 73% after 3 min; 7-78% after 3 min and 15 min; 9-81% after 1 min and 3 min.

at room temperature and the residue subjected to ¹H NMR analysis. The product nitrone was then crystallised. In view of the nearly quantitative transformation, the reaction mixture could be directly added to a solution of the dipolarophile for carrying out the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction. Nine *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones (1-9) were prepared during this study. Seven of these, viz. (1-7), were reported earlier. The two others, (8) and (9), had been mentioned earlier, with flash points(!) of 178.7 ± 18.8⁹ and 187.9 ± 29.70¹⁰ respectively, but not characterised. These two have been prepared in the course of the present work and fully characterised.

¹H NMR analysis showed that for most of the aromatic aldehydes the conversion to nitrone was essentially complete within one minute. Thus the formation of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones under microwave irradiation conditions was faster than those of *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones¹¹. The results are given in Table 1. However, the reaction rate diminished when the strongly electron-donating *para*-substituent methoxy group was present. The reaction rate also slowed down on dilution of the reaction mixture with chlorobenzene. Prolonging reaction times sometimes caused decomposition.

The ¹H NMR analyses of typical examples are mentioned below. The reaction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde with phenylhydroxylamine were monitored by observing the 300 MHz ¹H NMR intensities of the following proton signals : *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde – δ 9.98 (s, CHO), 7.99 and 7.82 (d each, 8.4 Hz, H-2,6 and H-3,5); *C*-

(4'-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitronone – δ 7.88 (s, CH), 7.72 (dd, 7.5, 2.2, ring A, H-2,6), 7.41–7.44 (m, A, H-3,4,5), 8.32 (d, 8.5, B, H-2,6), 7.40 (d, 8.5, B, H-3,5); *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde – δ 10.15 (s, CHO), 8.38 and 8.07 (d each, 8.7 Hz, H-2,6 and H-3,5); *C*-(4'-nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitronone – (8.07 (s, CH), 7.77 (dd, 7.6, 2.3, ring A, H-2,6), 7.49–7.52 (m, A, H-3,4,5), 8.29 (d, 9.0, B, H-2,6) and 8.54 (d, 9.0, B, H-3,5).

The synthesis of the new series of *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones (10 to 14), was achieved from the appropriate aromatic aldehyde and *N*-4-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine under similar microwave irradiation conditions. From ¹H NMR analysis of aliquots taken after 1 min intervals, it was found that maximum yields were obtained within a few minutes. However, the yields were in general lower than those for the corresponding *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones. Prolonging reaction times sometimes caused decomposition of the nitrone formed and lowering of yields. The results are given in Table 2. These nitrones were recrystallised from ethanol and characterised from their ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and FT IR spectra.

The ¹H NMR analyses of typical examples are mentioned below. The reactions of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde with *N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)hydroxylamine were similarly monitored by 300 MHz ¹H NMR intensities of the following proton signals : *C*-(4''-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitronone – δ 7.85 (s, CH), 8.13 (d, 9.1, ring A, H-2,6), 7.69 (d, 9.1, A, H-3,5), 8.30 (d, 8.8, ring B, H-2,6),

Table 2. Microwave irradiation assisted synthesis of *C*-aryl-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrones

Sl. no.	Substituted benzaldehyde R-C ₆ H ₄ CHO;	Nitrones obtained	Reaction times in minutes NMR monitoring of percentage yield				Isolated ^d percentage yield and reaction ^e time in minutes	
			1 min	2 min	3 min	4 min		
1.	H	10	67	68	66	91.5	62	2
2.	4-NO ₂	11	64	53	51	-	58	1
3.	4-Cl	12	42	-	43	44	37	1
4.	4-Br	13	58	-	-	55	52	1
5.	Cinnamaldehyde	14	73	76	-	72	73	2

^dFrom a second set of experiments – other than those used for monitoring.

Note : On working up after microwave irradiation, isolated yield were as follows – after 1 min microwave irradiation 10,11-60%; 12-36%; 13-51%; after 2 min microwave irradiation 14-68%. Isolated yields by conventional procedure – after heating for 3 h at 60–65° in ethanol and allowing to stand in the refrigerator at 10 °C overnight, isolated yield 10,11,14-58%; 12-32%; 13-55%.

7.39 (d, 8.8, B, H-3,5), *C*-(4''-nitrophenyl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrone – δ 7.98 (s, CH), 7.68 and 7.44 (d, each, 8.8, ring A, H-2,6 and H-3,5), 8.10 and 8.23 (d, each, 9.1, B, H-2,6 and H-3,5).

Some compounds of this series of *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones were also synthesised in our laboratory by the conventional procedure, which consisted of heating the reactants at 60–65 °C in ethanolic solution for 3 h. Yields were somewhat lower by using the conventional procedure compared with the microwave irradiation assisted procedure. Some decomposition was also noted.

We believe that the microwave irradiation assisted procedure developed by us for the synthesis of *C,N*-diarylnitrones is the method of choice in view of the higher yields obtained, short reaction times and the cleanness and ease of operation.

Spectroscopic analyses of the *C,N*-diarylnitrones :

Though there are some scattered reports of spectroscopic properties of *C,N*-diarylnitrones¹², systematic studies have not been undertaken to our knowledge. While characterising the nitrones synthesised during this work, detailed IR, 300 MHz ¹H NMR investigations of all the compounds were carried out. In addition, 75.5 MHz ¹³C NMR spectra of several of the nitrones obtained were recorded and MS analyses of selected examples done.

The IR spectra of the nitrones (1 to 14) were recorded in KBr discs with a FT-IR spectrophotometer, with a resolution of 0.5 cm⁻¹. Nitrones exhibit two characteristic bands, corresponding to the N→O and C=N bond stretching vibrations. In the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl aldonitrones (1 to 9) the N→O band appears at 1175–1192 cm⁻¹. This band is observed

at 1185 cm⁻¹ in *C,N*-diphenylnitronone. Aromatic substituent effects are small, except in the *C*-(4'-methoxy)nitronone, where this band appears at 1175.5 cm⁻¹. The N→O band in the *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones appears at 1158–1197 cm⁻¹, the absorption for the parent *C*-phenylnitronone appearing at 1158.5 cm⁻¹, at about 27 cm⁻¹ less than the corresponding nitronone in the *N*-phenyl series. The C=N absorption appears between 1544–1600 cm⁻¹ for the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones and between 1579–1590 cm⁻¹ for the *C*-aryl-*N*-(4'-chlorophenyl)nitrones. The position of this absorption seems to be more susceptible to variation in *C*-aryl substitution in the former series. In the *N*-phenyl series, this band occurs at 1545 cm⁻¹ in the parent *C,N*-diphenylnitrones, shifting to 1594.5 cm⁻¹ in the *C*-(4'-nitrophenyl) compound. The N→O band in the corresponding *N*-methylnitrones appears at smaller wave-numbers, viz. at 1159–1185 cm⁻¹.

Mass spectral fragmentation of *C,N*-diarylnitronone :

The mass spectra of typical *C,N*-diarylnitrones were studied. A summary of the mass spectral fragmentation which *C,N*-diarylnitrones undergo is presented in Scheme 1. There are previous reports on the mass spectra of variously substituted and deuterated *C,N*-diarylnitrones¹³. In all the spectra a diagnostic fragment appears at M⁺-16 resulting from the loss of oxygen. A summary of the MS fragmentation which *C,N*-diarylnitrones undergo is presented in Scheme 1, using *C,N*-diphenylnitronone as the example. The presence of the benzoyl cation requires oxygen migration from nitrogen to carbon, presumably by the intermediacy of an oxaziridine which rearranges to an amide, which fragments to PhC≡O⁺. In addition to this in spectra of most nitrones, the biphenylene radical cation and the 2-substituted benzisoxazolium cation are observed.

Scheme 1

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of *C*-(4-nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitronium is given in Scheme 2. The fragmentation pattern is very similar to that of *C,N*-diphenylnitronium and most of the characteristic patterns are perceived here, e.g. the loss of oxygen and the rearrangement to an oxaziridine. However, the formation of a fragment corresponding to $\text{O}_2\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CHO}$ from the rearranged amide is not observed – this is explicable on the basis of the relative inability of the electron-deficient ring to support the generation of a positive charge by the loss of an electron. The formation

of a nitrophenylene fragment is also not observable for a similar reason.

The 300 MHz ^1H NMR and 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR spectra of these two series of nitrones were recorded. The nitronium CH proton appears as a sharp singlet at $-\delta$ 7.9 in most of the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones (1-14) about 0.6 ppm downfield of the position in *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones. This signal was deshielded by 0.2 ppm in the *C*-(4-nitrophenyl) and *C*-(3-nitrophenyl)nitrones and slightly shielded (by \sim 0.05 ppm) in the *C*-(4-methoxyphenyl)nitrones. Due to restricted rotation on account of the *ortho*-methoxy group, the nitronium CH proton in **8** falls in the deshielding region of the methoxyl substituent in conformation A and is deshielded by 0.4 ppm to δ 8.30.

The 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR of some selected *C,N*-diaryl nitrones were recorded. The characteristic signal for all these nitrones is the $\text{CH}=\text{N}^+-\text{O}^-$ proton; this appeared in the region δ 132.0–134.4. For the *C,N*-diphenylnitrones this signal appeared at δ 134.2, introduction of the *para*-substituents caused slight upfield shifts. Replacement of *N*-phenyl by a *N*-(4'-chlorophenyl) group did not result in changes of the chemical shift of this carbon. Complete assignments were made on the basis of DEPT spectra, considerations of

Scheme 2

substituent chemical shifts (SCS) and from inter-comparisons among the spectra of the compounds investigated.

Experimental

A BPL-Sanyo model domestic microwave oven BMO-700T was used at a power setting of about 1200 Watts for the work. NMR samples were analysed in CDCl_3 solution using a Bruker AM-300L NMR spectrometer. IR spectra were recorded by a Perkin-Elmer RX-I FT IR spectrometer with a resolution of 0.5 cm^{-1} . Spectroscopic and analytical results were in agreement with expectations for the synthesised nitrones. Percentage contents of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen of new nitrones were obtained and found to be in agreement with the calculated values, only these are reported below. Isolated percentage yields are given in Tables 1 and 2 and are not repeated here.

General procedure : In a typical experiment the *N*-arylhydroxylamine (2.2 mmol), and the aromatic aldehyde (1.6 mmol) were taken in anhydrous dichloromethane (5–6 ml) in a 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask and subjected to microwave irradiation for periods usually varying from 1 to 4 min; on occasion this was extended to 15 min. A cooling device resembling a cold finger filled with ice was fitted on the top of the flask. At the end of the reaction period the reaction mixture was diluted with chloroform (15–20 mL), filtered and evaporated to dryness in a rotary evaporator. The residue was analysed by 300 MHz ^1H NMR. The nitrone was then crystallised from ethanol, methanol or petrol-benzene. The nitrones were characterised from their ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, mass spectra and FT IR spectra and comparison with authentic samples for the known nitrones available in our laboratory.

For preparative purposes the reactions could be scaled up 5 times, without change in reaction conditions and isolated yields.

C,N-Diphenylnitrone (1) :

White crystals from ethanol, m.p. 115° (lit. 114° ¹⁴). IR : $\nu = 1545$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1185 (m, N-O), 1068 (m, C-N), 762, 683.5 (s, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.91 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.76 (2H, dd, J 7.8, 3.0, A,H-2,6), 7.44–7.47 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.39 (2H, dd, J 7.7, 3.6, B,H-2,6), 7.44–7.47 (3H, m, B,H-3,4,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 134.2 ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 149.1 (A,C-1), 121.6 (A,C-2,6), 128.9 (A,C-3,5), 129.5 (A,C-4), 130.7 (B,C-1), 128.5 (B,C-2,6), 128.9 (B,C-3,5), 129.7 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(4-Nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (2) :

Bright yellow flakes from ethanol, m.p. 188° (lit. 187° –

189° ¹⁵). IR : $\nu = 1594.5$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1189 (m, N-O), 1074 (s, C-N), 772, 688 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring), 859 (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; MS (EI) : $m/z =$ (242 M^+), 241 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}$), 226 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{O}$), 195 (241 NO_2), 179 (226- $\text{NO}_2 - \text{H}$), 104 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3 - \text{NO}_2$), 91 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 8.10 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.77 (2H, dd, J 7.7, 2.4, A,H-2,6), 7.47–7.52 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.54 (2H, d, J 9.0, B,H-2,6), 8.29 (2H, d, J 9.0, B,H-3,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 132.1 ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 149.0 (A,C-1), 121.7 (A,C-2,6), 129.2 (A,C-3,5), 130.6 (A,C-4), 136.3 (B,C-1), 129.3 (B,C-2,6), 123.9 (B,C-3,5), 148.1 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(3-Nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (3) :

Yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 152° (lit. 152 – 153° ¹⁶). IR : $\nu = 1600$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1188.5 (m, N-O), 1062.5 (m, C-N), 773.5, 669.5 (1,3-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 8.10 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.78 (2H, dd, J 7.5, 2.3, A,H-2,6), 7.47–7.50 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 9.20 (1H, s, B,H-2), 7.65 (1H, t, J 8.0, B,H-5), 7.65 (1H, t, J 8.0, B,H-5), 8.29 (1H, d, J 8.0, B,H-6) ppm.

C-(4-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (4) :

White needles from ethanol, m.p. 154° (lit. 152 – 154° ¹⁷). IR : $\nu = 1600$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1185.5 (m, N-O), 1072 (s, Ar-Cl), 764, 686.5 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring), 842 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.90 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.72 (2H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5, A,H-2,6), 7.41–7.44 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.32 (2H, d, J 8.5, B,H-2,6), 7.40 (2H, d, J 8.5, B,H-3,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.2 ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 148.8 (A,C-1), 121.5 (A,C-2,6), 128.7 (A,C-3,5), 129.2 (A,C-4), 129.9 (B,C-1), 130.0 (B,C-2,6), 129.0 (B,C-3,5), 136.1 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(3-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (5) :

White crystals from ethanol, m.p. 115° (lit. 115 – 117° ¹⁴). IR : $\nu = 1561$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1192 (s, N-O), 1070 (s, Ar-Cl), 773, 682. (m, mono-substituted benzene ring), 897, 819 (m, 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.90 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.74 (2H, dd, J 7.6, 2.6, A,H-2,6), 7.42–7.50 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.60 (1H, s, B,H-2), 8.16 (1H, dt, J 6.9, 1.5, B,H-4), 7.48 (1H, t, J 7.2, B,H-5), 8.30 (1H, d, J 8.0, B,H-6) ppm.

C-(4-Bromophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (6) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 162° (lit. 162 – 164° ¹⁵). IR : $\nu = 1544.5$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1185.5 (s, N-O), 1069 (m, Ar-Br), 841 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 764, 685.5 (s, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.89 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+<$), 7.75 (2H, dd, J 7.6, 3.0, A,H-2,6),

7.47–7.49 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.28 (2H, d, *J* 8.6, B,H-2,6), 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 8.6, B,H-3,5) ppm.

C-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (7) :

Yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 116° (lit. 116–117°¹⁴). IR : $\nu = 1596$ (s, $>C=N^+<$), 1253 (s, C-O-C), 1176 (s, N-O), 1063 (m, C-N), 845, (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 762.5, 684 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.84 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 3.66 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 7.75 (2H, dd, *J* 8.2, 2.0, A,H-2,6), 7.45–7.48 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 8.39 (2H, d, *J* 7.2, B,H-2,6), 7.00 (2H, d, *J* 7.2, B,H-3,5) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.6 ($-CH=N^+<$), 55.0 ($-OCH_3$), 148.6 (A,C-1), 121.2 (A,C-2,6), 130.8 (A,C-3,5), 129.2 (A,C-4), 123.6 (B,C-1), 128.7 (B,C-2,6), 113.7 (B,C-3,5), 161.2 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrone (8) :

Pale yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 175° (Found : C, 73.49; H, 5.86; N, 6.06. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₃NO₂ : C, 73.99; H, 5.76; N, 6.16%). IR : $\nu = 1593.5$ (s, $>C=N^+<$), 1247 (m, C-O-C), 1186 (m, N-O), 1072 (m, C-N), 761, 688 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring), 762.5 (s, 1,2-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 8.30 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 3.78 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 7.67 (2H, dd, *J* 7.4, 3.0, A,H-2,6), 7.35–7.37 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 8.3, B,H-3), 7.37 (1H, t, *J* 5.5, B,H-4), 6.99 (1H, t, *J* 7.7, B,H-5), 9.40 (1H, d, *J* 8.0, B,H-6) ppm.

C-Cinnamoyl-*N*-phenylnitrone (9) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 140° (Found : C, 80.39; H, 5.96; N, 6.07. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₃NO : C, 80.69; H, 5.86; N, 6.27%). IR : $\nu = 1590$ (s, $>C=N^+<$), 1189.5 (s, N-O), 1052.5 (s, C-N), 745, 685 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 10.9, $-CH=N^+<$), 7.71 (1H, dd, *J* 11.0, 6.6, H- α), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 11.0, H- β), 7.75 (2H, dd, *J* 7.7, 2.4, A,H-2,6), 7.43–7.46 (3H, m, A,H-3,4,5), 7.57 (2H, dd, *J* 7.1, 3.0, B,H-2,6), 7.37–7.40 (3H, m, B,H-3,4,5) ppm.

C-Phenyl-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (10) :

White flakes from ethanol, m.p. 154° (lit. 152–154°¹⁸). IR : $\nu = 1579$ (m, $>C=N^+<$), 1158.5 (m, N-O), 1089.5 (s, Ar-Cl), 829 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 750, 665 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.77 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 8.14 (2H, d, *J* 7.9, A,H-2,6), 7.78 (2H, d, *J* 7.9, A,H-3,5), 8.53 (2H, dd, *J* 6.8, 3.0, B,H-2,6), 7.36–7.43 (3H, m, B,H-3,4,5) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 75.5 MHz) : 134.4 ($-CH=N^+<$), 147.7 (A,C-1), 123.1 (A,C-2,6), 129.9 (A,C-3,5), 135.9 (A,C-4), 131.1 (B,C-1), 128.7 (B,C-2,6), 129.1 (B,C-3,5), 130.6 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(4-Nitrophenyl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (11) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 188° (Found : C, 56.34; H, 3.19; N, 10.02. Calcd. for C₁₃H₉N₂O₃Cl : C, 56.43; H, 3.28; N, 10.12%). IR : $\nu = 1590$ (m, $>C=N^+<$), 1512, 1336 (s, Ar-NO₂), 1178 (m, N-O), 1078 (m, Ar-Cl), 830 (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.98 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 7.68 (2H, d, *J* 8.8, A,H-2,6), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 8.8, A,H-3,5), 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 9.1, B,H-2,6), 8.23 (2H, d, *J* 9.1, B,H-3,5) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 75.5 MHz) : 132.0 ($-CH=N^+<$), 140.0 (A,C-1), 123.0 (A,C-2,6), 129.5 (A,C-3,5), 136.8 (A,C-4), 136.0 (B,C-1), 129.3 (B,C-2,6), 123.9 (B,C-3,5), 148.3 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(4-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (12) :

Light orange needles from ethanol, m.p. 172° (lit. 170–172°¹⁶). IR : $\nu = 1587$ (m, $>C=N^+<$), 1182 (m, N-O), 1084 (s, Ar-Cl), 832.5 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.85 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 8.13 (2H, d, *J* 9.1, A,H-2,6), 7.69 (2H, d, *J* 9.1, A,H-3,5), 8.30 (2H, d, *J* 8.9, B,H-2,6), 7.39 (2H, d, *J* 8.9, B,H-3,5) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.4 ($-CH=N^+<$), 142.3 (A,C-1), 123.8 (A,C-2,6), 129.0 (A,C-3,5), 135.3 (A,C-4), 133.3 (B,C-1), 130.2 (B,C-2,6), 127.1 (B,C-3,5), 140.0 (B,C-4) ppm.

C-(4-Bromophenyl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (13) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 210° (Found : C, 50.02; H, 2.98; N, 4.40. Calcd. for C₁₃H₉NOClBr : C, 50.27; H, 2.92; N, 4.50%). IR : $\nu = 1580.5$ (s, $>C=N^+<$), 1170 (m, N-O), 1069 (s, Ar-Cl), 831 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.78 (1H, s, $-CH=N^+<$), 8.07 (2H, d, *J* 9.0, A,H-2,6), 7.50 (2H, d, *J* 9.0, A,H-3,5), 8.15 (2H, d, *J* 6.7, B,H-2,6), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* 6.7, B,H-3,5) ppm.

C-Cinnamoyl-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitrone (14) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 205° (Found : C, 69.68; H, 4.58; N, 5.23. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₂NOCl : C, 69.90; H, 4.69; N, 5.43%). IR : $\nu = 1589$ (m, $>C=N^+<$), 1197 (m, N-O), 1055 (s, Ar-Cl), 827.5 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 741, 674.5 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ , 300 MHz) : 7.43 (1H, d, *J* 7.7, $CH=N^+<$), 6.66 (1H, dd, *J* 16.2, 9.0, H- α), 7.1 (1H, d, *J* 16.2, H- β), 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 6.9, A,H-2,6), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* 6.9, A,H-3,5), 7.50 (2H, dd, *J* 7.4, 3.0, B,H-2,6), 7.36–7.38 (3H, m, B,H-3,4,5) ppm.

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